

Investigating the Structural Model of the Relationship between Hardiness and Social Anxiety, Self-esteem and Motivation in Teaching among Arab Novice and Intern Teachers

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ABSTRACT: The current study sought to investigate the structural model of the relationship between hardiness and social anxiety, self-esteem and motivation in teaching among 298 novice and intern teachers in Israeli Arab schools. The participants filled out questionnaires that included demographic details, and measures of hardiness and the three mentioned variables. A structural equation analysis indicated moderate and statistically significant positive direct effects of hardiness on motivation in teaching and self-esteem, while a negative direct effect of hardiness was found on social anxiety. It was also found that hardiness explained 25% of the variance of motivation in teaching ($p < .05$), 22% of the variance of social anxiety, and 28% of the variance of self-esteem. Results of the structural equations analysis show that the theoretical model fits the data, and that the research hypotheses were confirmed. Future interventions for novice and intern teachers should focus primarily on increasing their hardiness levels in order to reduce their social anxiety levels, and raise their self-esteem and motivation in teaching.

Keywords: Hardiness, social anxiety, motivation in teaching, novice and intern teachers, Arab society.

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1. Introduction

The main challenge of the education system is to train good teachers and make sure they stay in the system. This challenge is not simple in view of high dropout rates of novice teachers from the education system, especially among good teachers. In Israel, dropout rates up to the third year after qualifying are between 21% in elementary schools and 40% in middle schools, and up to the fifth year after qualifying – between 26% in elementary schools and 46% in middle schools (Knesset, 2017).

The literature points to a gap between the expectations of novice teachers and the reality that greets them (reality shock) - "the shock of the living classroom" (Dicker & Parker, 2015). Some argue that a failed entry into the teaching position and the burden of difficulties are the main causes of teachers dropping out of the profession in their first years of work.

According to researchers (Ellison & Woods, 2020; Jackson, 2021), the reasons for the existing gap between the training process and the practical work in the field include cognitive, educational, emotional-social, personal, and structural-systemic aspects.

Despite the state's large investment in teacher training and recruitment, teachers dropping out of the teaching profession has been an expanding phenomenon in recent decades. It is assumed that the more a perception of continuum is created between novice teachers' training period and their absorption process in the education system, in addition to in-depth exposure in dedicated workshops for the novice teachers in the socio-emotional and educational factors, the better their chances are to succeed and persevere in teaching (Flores, 2017; Gu, 2018).

Of the above factors, hardiness, self-esteem, and motivation in teaching are among the key elements that assist in the absorption process of novice teachers (Shani, 2018). Strengthening the novice teachers' hardiness through absorption accompaniment programs, and structured, consistent and intensive professional development programs, can prevent dropouts and improve perseverance in the system (Beutel et al., 2019; Chonnakarn & Arnont, 2020; Schatz-Oppenheimer, 2017).

One of the main investigated phenomena is hardiness, which is a personality characteristic (Kobasa, 1979; Kobasa, 1982), and acts as a resistance resource against life stressor events. In Kobasa's model, hardiness is a structure that is composed of three components: work and personal commitment, personal sense of control in time of events and consequences, and an internal belief that change is a challenge and an opportunity for evolution and not a threat.

In the teaching world, the scientific literature contains a variety of studies that investigated different aspects related to the hardiness phenomenon, its sources and implications (Baron & Baron, 2019; Beutel et al., 2019; Chonnakarn & Arnont, 2020; Ellison & Woods, 2020; Jackson, 2021; Kärner et al., 2021).

The education system and its various components, educational institutions of various kinds, and teaching staff (especially teachers at the beginning of their teaching career, as well as teachers with more experience), and by virtue of being exposed to acute natural and man-made disturbances, depends greatly on its level of hardiness, to continue to fulfil its purpose even after the occurrence of such disturbances. The education system cannot prevent, reduce or postpone serious disorders. It can indeed strengthen the personal and systemic hardiness of all its components.

In addition, the responsibilities of the new teacher expand, over time, and encounter additional challenges. Therefore, for teachers starting their teaching career to develop and function well, they must develop emotional, social and motivational growth resources that will enable coping with challenges and difficulties. It is about promoting optimal social-emotional development because the struggle is not only pedagogical, but also systemic and emotional. A characteristic that could help these diverse coping processes and empower novice teachers is hardiness, which consists of three elements: commitment, control, and challenge (Kobasa, 1979; 1982).

Most research on novice and intern teachers' hardiness and its relationships with demographic, socio-emotional and educational factors have so far been conducted on Western populations; few such studies were conducted in Israel with emphasis on the Arab society. Therefore, in the current study, the researchers chose demographic variables from the world of teaching, relevant to the population of novice and intern teachers, such as gender, age, study track, teaching specialization, teaching status, teaching experience, religious-ethnic background, and other socio-emotional and educational factors related to the professional training of teachers at the beginning of their career, such as social anxiety, self-esteem and motivation in teaching.

Despite significant investments in teacher training and recruitment, the high dropout rates of novice teachers, particularly within the first few years of their careers, remain a critical challenge in the Israeli education system, especially among teachers in the Arab society. This issue is compounded by a gap between the expectations of novice teachers and the realities they face in the classroom, leading to what is often referred to as "reality shock." This shock, combined with the additional responsibilities and emotional challenges that new teachers encounter, contributes to their decision to leave the profession.

Existing research suggests that hardiness—a personality trait comprising commitment, control, and challenge—can play a vital role in helping novice teachers navigate these challenges and persist in their careers. However, most studies on the relationship between hardiness and factors such as social anxiety, self-esteem, and motivation in teaching have focused on Western populations, with limited research on Arab society in Israel. There is a need to investigate how hardiness influences these socio-emotional and motivational factors among novice and intern teachers in this specific context to develop targeted interventions that can reduce dropout rates and enhance teacher retention. This study aims to address this gap by examining the structural model of the relationships between hardiness, social anxiety, self-esteem, and motivation in teaching among novice and intern teachers in Israeli Arab schools.

Therefore, the main research question was: Does hardiness affect social anxiety, self-esteem and motivation in teaching among novice and intern teachers from the Arab society?

2. Characteristics of the Arab Education System and Teacher Training in Israel

The Arabs in Israel are a numerical minority and a sociological minority at the same time. The Arab population today numbers more than 1.8 million people, 20.8% of the total population (Central Bureau of Statistics [CBS], 2017). Arab society in Israel is traditional-patriarchal in nature, and one can find teachers with a variety of approaches in the context of hardiness. The Arab education system is typically very conservative, and any changes are minute and slow (Jabreen & Agbariya, 2010).

The Arab education system's complex reality causes novice teachers to be busy most of the time with survival and coping with feelings of frustration, helplessness, disappointment, and loneliness – instead of learning and development (Abu-Saad et al.,

2020). The education system in the Arab sector has suffered from neglect and discrimination, manifested in large gaps between it and the education system in the Jewish sector, both in resources and in achievements (Abu-Saad et al., 2020; Gharrah, 2016).

Among the reasons for the significant gap that still exists between the two populations are the teaching methods and learning skills of schools in Arab society relative to schools in Hebrew education. In general, the teaching method in Arab society does not encourage critical and independent thinking patterns. In addition, the study societies in Arab schools lead to the expectation that the Arab student receives assistance from teachers in coping with learning difficulties (Abu-Saad et al., 2020; Gharrah, 2016).

Entry into teaching in the Israeli education system consists of three stages: a. Practical experience phase (student teachers): To become a teacher in Israel, the student studies for four years and receives a Bachelor's degree; b. Internship phase (intern teachers): The first year of a teacher's work is called the internship year, and according to Ministry of Education instructions, a mentor teacher from the school is attached to this teacher; and c. Accompanying phase (novice teachers): An intern teacher who successfully passed the internship process, and continued to work for a second year as a teacher is called a novice teacher and has a permanent license to practice teaching (Ronen & Weisblit, 2021).

Research on the training of Arab teachers in Israel has not addressed teacher training from its pedagogical or demographic and socio-emotional aspects, but has focused on political-social aspects (Abu-Saad et al., 2020). This situation calls for professional intervention, which can help the beginning teacher to survive the first year of work, can accelerate his or her professional identity process, and can prevent dropping out of the profession at the initial stages of teaching.

Hardiness and Its Implications

Kobasa (1979) coined the term hardiness to describe a certain personality type that is 'hardy' in times of pressure, is active and caring, and acts according to life's circumstances. The basis for this is mental health. Namely, hardiness was determined as a personality-based tendency to diminish the impact of stressful life events by optimistic cognitive appraisals and decisive coping actions (Kobasa, 1982). Hardiness is used to explain how and why certain people retain their mental health in face of adversity (Chonnakarn & Arnont, 2020; Kobasa, 1979).

This concept was defined as a constellation of three dispositions or elements – commitment, control and challenge – that are part of an integral structure that is larger than the sum of its parts (Shani, 2018). In addition, hardiness has been shown to be a buffer in the stress/illness relationship independent of other known buffers such as social support and exercise (Kobasa, 1982). The combined hardy attitudes of commitment, control, and challenge constitute the best available operationalization of existential courage (Maddi, 1988).

Kobasa (1982) developed the concept of hardiness into three main bilateral and interdependent elements: a. Commitment/engagement – interest and involvement in one's surroundings (work, family, leisure activities, and world affairs); b. Control – a sense of

influence on the environment and one's life events; and c. Challenge – faith in and feeling that new situations, changes and different experiences are an incentive and challenge for growth and development rather than a threat.

Recently, Chonnakarn and Arnont (2020) defined hardiness as the ability to successfully cope and adapt to stress and crisis situations by means of flexibility, which enables one to maneuver or regulate emotional and physiological reactions, in order to match the reaction to the environment's changing demands. People with high hardiness were found to recover more quickly, both physically and mentally, after crises. Along the same line, Jackson (2021) defined hardiness as one's ability to cope with difficulties, and come out strengthened and with insights, to bounce back quickly from a stressful situation, to recover from negative experiences, and to flexibly adapt to life's changing demands. A relationship has been found between hardiness and life satisfaction and lower levels of depression and anxiety (Jackson, 2021).

Another concept, which we did not focus on in the present study but appears in the scientific literature and overlaps the concept of hardiness, is the resilience concept. Some researchers characterize resilience as a state that varies depending on an individual's personal characteristics and experiences (Masten & Tellegen, 2012), referring to a dynamic process of adaptation to adverse and unpleasant experiences (Masten, 2001), but generally refers to an individual's capacity in the face of stressful events (Yi-Frazier et al., 2009), and a pattern of functioning indicative of positive adaptation in the context of risk or adversity. Resilience can be observed in various people and different developmental stages including childhood, adolescence, and adulthood (Davis et al., 2009).

Rutter (1987) was among the first to mention the implications of hardiness; primarily, that it protects people from developing psychopathological disorders, and provides them with higher self-esteem, a sense of self-efficacy, problem-solving skills, and satisfying relationships with the environment. Hardiness acts as a buffer to major life stressors (Maddi et al., 2006). High hardiness is associated with lower psychological distress and higher quality of life (Hoge et al., 2007), and the person high in hardiness is marked by increased commitment, sense of control, and challenge (Johnsen et al., 2009).

Hardiness is considered one of the key elements that assist in the absorption process of novice teachers, in affinity to organizational commitment and management style (Shani, 2018; Dallasheh & Zubeidat, 2021). Therefore, in a period of studies and career development, novice teachers and interns should acquire certain levels of hardiness, to find inner peace, strength, focus, and flexibility. In addition, studies, which examined the interactions between self-efficacy and hardiness of interns and novice teachers, and stress and burnout factors, found a reciprocal relationship between them (Gu, 2018).

The Conceptual Framework and the Research Model

Today, there is recognition that cultivating cognitive abilities (e.g., intelligence, coping skills) and knowledge are not enough for teachers to be able to function well and feel good in the education system. It is clear that in order for novice and intern teachers to develop and function well, they must develop emotional, social and motivational growth

resources that enable prosperity, mental well-being, and dealing with challenges and absorption difficulties (Dallasheh & Zubeidat, 2021).

Wardani (2020) revealed that academic hardiness plays a direct role in developing participants' psychological well-being. Other researchers (Shani, 2018; Dallasheh & Zubeidat, 2021) highlighted the importance of studying the relationships between hardiness and other socio-emotional and educational concepts. Along this line, other studies revealed relationships between hardiness and social anxiety (Chen-Yi & Yuhsuan, 2019), self-esteem (Fernández-Castillo et al., 2022) and teaching motivation (Lee & Sung, 2023). These concepts are relevant to help dealing with the difficulties and pressures of teaching, and improve the optimal absorption process of novice teachers.

Based on this recognition, many in the world have turned to concepts and programs known as social-emotional learning (SEL) in order to impart skills in this field (Denston et al., 2022). Hence, the choice of variables from the socio-emotional and educational world in the current study as follows:

- a. Social anxiety. The American Psychiatric Association (2013) defined social anxiety as "marked fear or anxiety about one or more social situations in which the individual is exposed to possible scrutiny by others. Other researchers (Bi & Liu, 2019) have defined social anxiety as a fear of being negatively assessed by others in different social situations that require performance and social interaction with others. In this context, a negative relationship was found between social anxiety and hardiness (Chen-Yi & Yuhsuan, 2019), and further negative relationships were found between social anxiety and mental health, functional enjoyment, social functioning (academic and professional), and quality of life (Kashdan, 2002).
- b. Self-esteem. Self-esteem is defined as an organized set of characteristics that one attributes to oneself and acts accordingly (Fitts, 1965). The professional literature presents self-esteem as the individual's perception of him- or herself, which is constantly reinforced, and is perceived as self-judgement based on experiences of success or failure. This judgement can explain a long and varied list of behaviors such as obedience, morality, changing attitudes, interpersonal attraction, perversions, and help-giving (Lages et al., 2015). Recently, Khosravi and Namani (2022) revealed that self-compassion and psychological hardiness indirectly affected family cohesion through self-worth.
- c. Motivation in teaching. Promoting good-quality motivation processes in the educational context requires full cooperation between the school staff, which, in turn, requires building trust between the participants in various areas, mutual respect, and mutual status (Kaplan et al., 2011). High-level internal motivation of teachers and education workers significantly improves their sense of wellbeing, and their positive feelings when performing various work tasks. In the academic context, Wardani (2020) indicated that commitment, control, and challenges that reveal participants' ability to adapt to new academic demands can improve their individual ability to demonstrate their fully functioning self in completing academic demands and tolerating pressures. In this context, it was found that the internal motivation for teaching is one of the most significant for novice teachers' happiness and hardiness (Gaby & Kasumi, 2015).

The theoretical-empirical framework presented in this chapter provided an initial tool for building a theoretical model that reflects the relationships between hardiness as an independent variable, and social anxiety, self-esteem and motivation in teaching as

dependent variables, on which this study focuses. The conceptual model was designed on these theoretical foundations (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Research Conceptual Model.

The Present Study

The paucity of research on hardiness characteristics and its relationships with socio-emotional and educational factors, and the mentioned structural model, as well as the limited studies that used samples of novice and intern teachers from Israeli Arab society, motivated the authors to conduct this research.

The present study can contribute to understanding the nature of the relationships between hardiness and social anxiety, self-esteem and motivation in teaching, and investigating the structural model of the relationships between hardiness and these factors and among Arab novice teachers and teacher-interns. Investigating this issue among novice and intern teachers in the Arab education system could serve as a basis for relevant optimal absorption models like the one proposed by Authors (2021), and programs that include improving learning motivation processes and enhancing the hardiness of early career teachers, and training them in socio-emotional aspects.

In light of the above, the main goal of the present study is to investigate the structural model of the relationship between hardiness with social anxiety, self-esteem and motivation in teaching among Arab novice teachers and teacher-interns. In accordance with the research's main goal, several hypotheses will be tested that refer to the conceptual model described in Figure 1.

H1: Significant differences will be found in hardiness levels by various demographic variables (e.g., age, gender, and religious-ethnic background, study track, teaching specialization, teaching status, and teaching experience).

H2: Hardiness levels have a direct negative effect on social anxiety levels.

H3: Hardiness levels have a direct positive effect on self-esteem levels.

H4: Hardiness levels have a direct positive effect on motivation in teaching levels.

3. Method

This quantitative-correlative study focused on the relationships between demographic, socio-emotional and educational variables and hardiness among novice and intern teachers from Arab society in Israel. The independent variable is hardiness, and the dependent variables are gender, age, study track, teaching specialization, teaching status, teaching experience, religious-ethnic background, social anxiety, self-esteem and teaching motivation.

Sample

The research sample was obtained through convenience sampling to ensure an equal opportunity for teachers to take part in the present study. The sample was composed of 298 novice and intern teachers who participated in training and workshops in an Arab teacher-training college. There are limitations relating to the representativeness of this kind of sample. Convenience sampling is not often recommended for research due to the possibility of lack of representation of the population. However, it can be handy depending on the situation (Cohen & Arieli, 2011). Table 1 presents the general demographic data of the participants.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Novice and Intern Teachers (N=298).

Variable		N	%	Mean (\pm SD)
Age (in years)				26.09 (\pm 3.7)
Gender	Men	81	27.2%	
	Women	217	72.8%	
Religious-ethnic background	Muslim	194	65.5%	
	Christian	58	19.6%	
	Druze	44	14.9%	
Study track	Elementary School	149	51%	
	Middle & High School	143	49%	
Teaching status	Intern teachers	60	20.3%	
	Novice teachers	236	79.7%	
Teaching specialization	Humanities	137	51.7%	
	Sciences	127	47.9%	
Teaching experience	None	78	26.4%	
	1 year	95	32.1%	
	2 years	66	22.3%	
	3 years and more	57	19.3%	

Operationalization of Variables

The novice and intern teachers were asked to fill out the following questionnaires:

Hardiness Questionnaire

The original questionnaire (Kobasa, 1979) includes 71 items that represent attitudes towards life situations/events, and relate to the three elements of hardiness: commitment, control and challenge. The respondents were asked to note their agreement with each statement on a scale of 1 (do not agree at all) to 4 (agree completely). Sample items: "I love

diversity in my work"; "It is exciting to learn something about myself". The internal validity (Cronbach's alpha coefficient) of this questionnaire in the current research was .91. This questionnaire was chosen because it contains enough statements that measure the mentioned three elements of hardiness.

Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale – LSAS

This questionnaire (Liebowitz, 1987) was designed to measure social anxiety by means of examining social fear and social avoidance. The questionnaire includes 24 statements – 13 describe actions and 11 describe social interactions. The respondents' agreement or lack of agreement with the fear or anxiety statements is measured on a Likert scale of 1 (not at all) to 4 (very much), and their agreement with the avoidance statements on a Likert scale of 0 (never) to 3 (usually). Sample items: "Go to a party"; "Write while I'm being watched"; "Speak in public". The internal validity (Cronbach's alpha coefficients) of this questionnaire and its components social fear and social avoidance in the current research were .98, .95 and .96, respectively.

Rosenberg's Self-esteem Scale – RSES

This questionnaire (Rosenberg, 1965) includes ten statements that examine the respondents' self-esteem on a Likert scale of 1 (agree very much) to 4 (do not agree at all). The questionnaire examines two factors – positive self-esteem and negative self-esteem. Sample items: "I feel I have some positive qualities"; "I feel I don't have much to be proud of"; "I wish I had more self-esteem". The internal validity (Cronbach's alpha coefficient) of this questionnaire in the current research was .73.

Motivation in Teaching Questionnaire

This questionnaire was based on Friedman and Kess (2000) teacher's self-efficacy scale. Its goal is to examine the respondents' belief in their ability and desire to develop and control events that affect their environment and life on three measures: teaching tasks, in the school as an organization, and relationships with colleagues, students, and management. The questionnaire includes 29 items on a scale of 1 (disagree completely) to 6 (agree completely). The internal validity (Cronbach's alpha coefficient) of this questionnaire in the current research was .96.

Procedure and Ethics

The researchers explained the goals of the research to the novice teachers and interns, and requested their consent to answer the questionnaires. The guidelines to filling out the questionnaires were clarified without any undue influence on the participants. The questionnaires were all in Hebrew, and we saw no need to translate them into Arabic, assuming that the participants understood Hebrew well enough. The questionnaires were collected at the college, but not during lessons, and were coded and analyzed by the researchers at a later stage. The data collection process took place during November-December 2018. Fifteen teachers answered less than half of the statements, which forced the researchers to omit their data and not include them in the analyses.

It should be noted that, for ethical reasons, it was made clear to the participants that their replies were completely anonymous, and that any data they provided would be used

solely for the purpose of this study, and would not be transferred to a third party. In this context, the participant's consent was voluntary. We respected any participant's refusal to participate.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analyses designed to test the first research hypotheses were produced by comparing pairs of groups (e.g., specialization in teaching: humanities versus sciences) using the T-test, or comparing three or more groups (e.g., teaching experience: no experience, one year, two years and three years or more) using the F-test (factor analysis or one-way variance analysis).

In addition, to check the second, third and fourth hypotheses, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was performed with M-Plus software, which, in one statistical analysis, effectively examines holistic models that include complex relationships between their theoretic structures, and the complexity of direct effects of independent variables on dependent variables. M-Plus offers a wide choice of models, estimators, and algorithms in a program that has an easy-to-use interface and graphical displays of data and analysis results (Hallinger & Heck, 1998).

Structural equations are analyzed at the level of the individual, because the research participants were from different schools, and we did not find any participants belonging to the same school. In addition, structural equations analysis is performed in two stages: in the first stage, the measurement model is tested, and then the structural model of the study is tested. According to the literature, the model fit would be acceptable if the CFI values were no less than .90 and the RMSEA and SRMR values was no more than .08 (Kline, 2005).

4. Findings

Relationships between Hardiness and Other Variables

First, we calculated the means, standard deviations and the Pearson's correlation coefficients to examine the correlations between hardiness and the variables: social anxiety, social fear, social avoidance, self-esteem, and motivation in teaching of novice teachers and interns (see Table 2).

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Coefficients for the Relationships between Social Anxiety, Self-esteem and Motivation in Teaching Variables with Hardiness (N=298).

Variable	M	SD	Hardiness
Social anxiety	1.66	.73	-.22***
Social fear	1.64	.77	-.17**
Social avoidance	1.67	.76	-.27***
Self-esteem	2.17	.49	.32***
Motivation in teaching	3.63	.99	.39***
Teaching tasks Organization	3.74	1.19	.39***
Relationships	3.66	1.06	.24***
	3.17	0.87	.41***

p<.01, *p<.001

The results presented in Table 2 indicate a number of relationships:

1. A significant negative relationship between hardiness and social anxiety ($r_p = -.22$, $p < .001$); namely, the higher one's hardiness, the lower one's social anxiety is.
2. A significant negative relationship between hardiness and social fear ($r_p = -.17$, $p < .01$); namely, the higher one's hardiness, the lower one's social fear is.
3. A significant negative relationship between hardiness and social avoidance ($r_p = -.27$, $p < .001$); namely, the higher one's hardiness, the lower one's social avoidance is.
4. A significant positive relationship between hardiness and self-esteem ($r = .32$, $p < .001$); namely, the higher one's hardiness, the higher one's self-esteem is.
5. A significant positive relationship between hardiness and motivation in teaching ($r = .39$, $p < .001$); namely, the higher one's hardiness, the higher one's motivation in teaching is.
6. A significant positive relationship between hardiness and teaching tasks ($r = .39$, $p < .001$); namely, the higher one's hardiness, the higher one's teaching tasks are.
7. A significant positive relationship between hardiness and organization ($r = .24$, $p < .001$); namely, the higher one's hardiness, the higher one's organization is.
8. A significant positive relationship between hardiness and relationships ($r = .24$, $p < .001$); namely, the higher one's hardiness, the higher one's relationships are.

Differences in Hardiness Levels by Various Demographic Factors

As mentioned, hardiness was measured on a 0 (no hardiness) to 3 (high hardiness) scale. To check the second research hypotheses, we conducted t-tests for independent samples to examine the differences in hardiness between interns and novice teachers, and between interns and novice teachers who specialized in humanities versus those who specialized in sciences. In addition, we performed one-way ANOVA to examine the differences in hardiness between interns and novice teachers with varying years of experience as teachers. The results are presented in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: Comparison of Hardiness between Interns and Novice Teachers, and between Interns and Novice Teachers who Specialized in Humanities versus Sciences (N=298).

Variable	Status or specialization	N	Mean	SD	t
Hardiness	Intern teachers	60	2.18	.24	-3.69***
	Novice teachers	232	2.32	.26	
Hardiness	Humanities	136	2.33	.24	2.86**
	Sciences	126	2.24	.29	

** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$

As can be seen, a significant difference in hardiness was found between the two groups ($t(298) = -3.69$, *** $p < .001$). The average level of hardiness among novice teachers was higher than that of interns. Table 3 also shows that a significant difference was found between the hardiness of the two groups of specialization ($t(298) = 2.86$, ** $p < .01$). The hardiness among the humanities specialization was significantly higher than that of the sciences specialization.

Table 4: Comparison of Participants in Hardiness by Years of Experience in Teaching (N=298).

Variable	Teaching experience	N	Mean	SD	F
Hardiness	No experience	78	2.22	.23	2.79*
	One year	95	2.32	.24	
	Two years	63	2.27	.35	
	Three years or more	57	2.34	.25	

*p<.05

The results of the ANOVA test clearly show significant differences in the respondents' level of hardiness by years of experience teaching. Because the differences were significant in the analysis of variance tests, post-hoc Scheffé tests were conducted to compare pairs of comparisons. The result was significant for only one comparison – between novice teachers and interns with no experience, and the others.

Next, the differences in hardiness of novice teachers and interns by other demographic data (gender, study track, and religious-ethnic background) were examined by means of t-tests and ANOVA, but these produced no significant differences between the respondents' hardiness levels.

Estimation of the Measurement Model and Its Evaluation

A measurement model was constructed to examine the validity of the four scales before the hypothesized model was tested. The CFA results indicated that the model fit the

data well: $(\chi^2 = 153, df = 53, \frac{\chi^2}{df} = 2.85, CFI = .97, SRMR = .05, RMSEA = .06[.05,.07])$, and the loadings of the latent variables ranged from .77 to .92. This indicated acceptable construct validity for all scales, and inconsistency between the latent variables and the indicators.

Estimation of the Structural Model and Its Evaluation

To check the second, third and fourth research hypotheses, in this section, the findings referring to the examination of the structural model developed based on the theoretical and research literature in the field are presented. In order to test the empirical validity of the model, a structural equation analysis (SEM) was performed. The fit indices obtained from the structural analysis for the structural model are:

$$(\chi^2 = 153, df = 53, \frac{\chi^2}{df} = 2.85, CFI = .97, SRMR = .05, RMSEA = .06[.05,.07])$$

The findings indicate statistically significant loading coefficients ($p < .001$) higher than .70 of the observed variables on the latent variables. The loading of hardiness was between .77 and .87. Of the hardiness components, control had the highest loading. The loading coefficients on motivation were between .85 and .92, and the strongest loading was of relationships. Similarly, the components of social anxiety were between .80 and .82. That

is to say, the measures of the latent variables are a good reflection of the theoretic concepts in the model.

The results of the SEM analyses that are presented in Figure 2 will be discussed according to the research hypotheses. The direct effects of hardiness on respondents' social anxiety, self-esteem and motivation to teach are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: The Direct Effects of Hardiness on Social Anxiety, Self-esteem and Motivation in Teaching (N=298).

Variable	Estimate	Social anxiety	Self-esteem	Motivation in teaching
Hardiness	Non-standard estimate	***.20-	***.20	** .23
	Standard estimate	***.22-	***.20	** .30

P* < .05, P** < .01, P*** < .001

As can be seen in Table 5, the two expected positive effects of hardiness on motivation to teach and self-esteem were small and significant (B=.30, P<.001; B=.20, P<.001, respectively) (Cohen, 1988). In addition, the results show a direct negative effect of hardiness on social anxiety (B=-.22, P<.001). It was also found that hardiness explained 25% of the variance of motivation in teaching (p<.05), 22% of the variance of social anxiety, and 28% of the variance of self-esteem (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: The Structural Equation Model

5. Discussion and Conclusions

Research on hardiness among novice and intern teachers, and its relationships with demographic, socio-emotional, and academic-educational factors, has been receiving attention in recent years in the educational system with the objective to create a qualitative atmosphere that enhances the optimal absorption and reduces the dropout of teachers at the beginning in their career. These issues involved educators and other policy-makers at schools and in teacher-training institutions, who emphasize hardiness in their study programs.

What makes hardiness unique in the educational context is that it is a personality trait that moderates the negative effects of stress or mental distress related to the educational tasks of novice and intern teachers, increases one's adaptability, and serves as a 'mental immune system' against stress conditions (Day, 2018). Although hardiness is a personality trait, interventions can achieve changes when they help people encourage normal socio-emotional skills (e.g., self-efficacy, self-esteem, emotional intelligence), foster ways of coping, and strengthen the elements of commitment, challenge, and control (Beutel et al., 2019; Kobasa, 1982; Shani, 2018).

The first findings revealed significant negative relationships between hardiness and social anxiety, social fear, and social avoidance among the novice and intern teachers. In this context, hardiness had an indirect effect on procrastination through social anxiety (Chen-Yi & Yuhsuan, 2019). These results are compatible with previous research that reported that hardiness helps to overcome tense, stressful situations, reduces the negative effects of stress, increases one's ability to cope (Valliant, 2003), strengthens perseverance during stress and lessens mental health-related complaints (Thomassen et al., 2015). This supports previous work that found a negative relationship between social anxiety and hardiness (Kashdan, 2002; Zubeidat et al., 2019).

In addition, significant positive relationships between hardiness and self-esteem and motivation in teaching (including teaching tasks, relationships and organization) are compatible with previous findings that revealed the effect of internal motivation on the functioning of teacher trainees and interns, and on their sense of happiness and hardiness (Gaby & Kasumi, 2015). Furthermore, the more teacher-trainees and interns used strategies of active coping, their levels of motivation in teaching, hardiness, self-esteem and professional wellbeing increased (Magelinskaite et al., 2014).

It should be noted that hardiness, social anxiety, self-esteem and motivation in teaching constitute different concepts but are very closely linked to the academic world, especially for teachers at the beginning of their professional career, which explains the significant relationships between them (Baron & Baron, 2019; Ellison & Woods, 2020). Therefore, these findings are consistent with the current scientific literature, which emphasizes the overlap in the content of the concepts implied in this study (Kärner et al., 2021). The findings also emphasize that the higher the hardiness of teachers at the beginning of their carrier, the lower their levels of social anxiety and the higher their levels of self-esteem and motivation in teaching eventually are.

The findings related to the first hypothesis particularly indicated significant differences in hardiness associated with demographic elements concerned with the essence of the teaching profession, rather than other demographic elements. Significant differences were found by the respondents' teaching status and experience in teaching. In this context, the transition from being education students to interns and new teachers is sudden and dramatic (Piwowar et al., 2013). Specifically, it is a change from a protected, supportive environment to independent work that requires responsibility.

We also found that teachers who specialized in humanities showed higher levels of hardiness than teachers that specialized in sciences. It should be noted that interns and novice teachers specializing in sciences typically suffer more pressure and difficulties vis-à-

vis the school management and their students. In general, it has been reported that demographic, personal-emotional, employment-related, and organizational elements affect the integration of beginning teachers in the system, as well as their decision to leave the profession (Arbiv-Elyashiv & Zimmerman, 2015).

On the other hand, no significant relationships were found between gender, study track, or religious-ethnic background and the hardiness of the participants, who share the same culture, values, and customs. These findings contradict previous research that examined the issue of gender, which indicated that male students reported a significantly lower mean score on hardiness compared to female students (Sheard, 2009). The findings of Segal and Gilat's (2011) study of 526 teacher-interns in Israel are compatible with our current findings. They found no significant relationships between measures of personal wellbeing and demographic characteristics that are unrelated to the essence of teaching: age, family status, residence, and level of religiosity.

The findings associated with the second, third and fourth hypotheses - the effect of hardiness on social anxiety, self-esteem and motivation in teaching, respectively - revealed that the fit indices obtained from the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) indicated a good fit of the model, and meet the criteria defined in the literature (Hu & Bentler, 1999). It was also found that all the variables in the structural model explained 50% of the variance of the hardiness variable. It should be noted that the SEM results show that the theoretical model (Figure 2) fits the data, and all hypotheses were corroborated. These findings are consistent with the findings that examined the relationships between hardiness and the three variables mentioned above.

Along these lines, researchers (Chen-Yi & Yuhsuan, 2019) informed that students with higher levels of hardiness reported a lower frequency of procrastination behavior. It has been also found that compared with non-hardy subjects, hardy individuals react to stressful situations with considerably more psychological well-being (Hull et al., 1987). Khampirat (2020) showed that paternal education, hardiness, and future orientation have significant direct effects on students' career aspirations, while self-esteem has an indirect effect. In addition, Ismail et al. (2021) revealed that assertive teachers with higher hardiness experience less pressure and social anxiety from the relationships with parents and feedback from others than non-assertive teachers do.

Therefore, the training of future teachers should attempt to increase their levels of hardiness and, at the same time, improve the levels of other related variables, such as those examined in the present study. An optimal mentoring process is important to promote socio-emotional development (including hardiness) through imparting socio-emotional abilities that fit the type of interactions between interns and novice teachers and others in the education system. This is especially important, as the research revealed that hardiness interventions lead to beneficial outcomes (Leppin et al., 2014), and the changes are sustained (Vanhove et al., 2016).

A number of limitations of the current study should be noted: a. The authors studied only novice and intern teachers in the Arab sector, so it is impossible to know to what degree and why the problems of hardiness are allegedly more prevalent among Arab novice and intern teachers than Jewish ones; b. This study focused on novice and intern teachers

from one teacher training college, among whom there are many demographic differences; c. The current study is a cross-sectional questionnaire study in which the relevant variables were measured by means of self-reports. Accordingly, future studies in this context should try to use a mixed quantitative and qualitative study or a study that employs behavioral measures (e.g., by means of observation); and d. The researchers chose the optimal conditions – place and timing – for the respondents, and therefore the conclusions that were reached are specifically true for novice teachers and interns from the Arab society in the north of Israel, and they cannot be generalized to other areas of the country or other populations.

The necessary conclusions of the current study include: a. Educational training of novice and intern teachers must attempt to improve processes related to the status and the experience in teaching among teachers at the beginning of their career; b. The educational system should improve human-emotional processes, especially those related to raising the levels of hardiness among sciences teachers; c. Further interventions with interns and novice teachers should focus on increasing hardiness, self-esteem and motivation in teaching and reducing social anxiety levels; d. It seems that hardiness has an effect on certain socio-emotional and academic-educational factors; e. Professional training supports optimal development of novice teachers' hardiness, and contributes to their coping skills, increases their ability to make balanced decisions that help them survive the challenging period, and gradually contributes to the development of their professional identity.

6. References

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